

Thallic Thallium Oxidation of Quinol

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Thallic thallium and quinol have been found to form a complex having maximum absorbance at 470 m μ . The reaction with respect to each oxidant as well as to the organic substrate has been found to obey first order kinetics. The thermodynamic parameters in kinetics of oxidation process have been evaluated.

THOUGH the phenol and substituted phenols get oxidised easily by various oxidants¹⁻⁸, their mode of oxidation and products are not that simple. This paper describes the interesting results in Tl^{III} oxidation⁹⁻¹⁴ of quinol in acetic acid medium, not reported in the literature earlier.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR or pure reagent grade. Thallium(III) acetate was prepared according to the method reported earlier¹⁵. Triple distilled water was used throughout the experiments.

Kinetic measurements :

The solutions of required quantity of the reactants, prepared in fixed composition of acetic acid and water, were rapidly mixed at the desired thermostatic temperature.

The kinetics of the reaction were followed by withdrawing a known volume of the reaction mixture at various intervals of time into ice cold water to quench the reaction velocity. The unreacted Tl^{III} was then quickly estimated iodometrically^{16,17}.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : Stoichiometry of the reaction was studied by taking the substrate and the oxidant in excess, the former to judge the reaction steps during kinetic runs and the latter to judge overall oxidation product.

(a) It was observed that when the organic substrate was in known excess all the Tl^{III} was reduced to Tl^I with the formation of the same number of moles of *p*-benzoquinone. The experimental results (Δ Tl^{III}/ Δ quinol) lead to the following equation

(b) In order to study the overall oxidation products, thallic perchlorate was taken in place of thallic acetate so as to facilitate identification of ultimate oxidation product easily.

Thallic perchlorate was prepared by dissolving thallic oxide in perchloric acid of desired strength and Tl^{III} was estimated iodometrically. The reaction mixture containing a known excess of thallic perchlorate in perchloric acid over organic substrate was kept overnight and the unreacted oxidant was estimated iodometrically. The oxidation product was isolated and identified as *p*-benzoquinone by centrifuging the product with the excess of ether. On separating the ethereal layer and standing it for a few hours golden yellow prismatic crystals separated out, m.p. 116°.

Test for organic free radical : The presence of free radical formation was confirmed by adding methyl methacrylate to the reaction mixture from which oxygen was expelled by passing pure nitrogen. The onset of polymerisation was indicated by appearance of turbidity in the initially clear solution and increased with the progress of polymerisation.

Results and Discussion

The results of particular concentrations of thallic thallium oxidation of quinol are presented in Table 1. It is observed that the rate becomes kinetically immeasurable if attempt is made to deviate from the given concentration of either oxidant or of organic substrate.

The reaction exhibits a total second order, and first order with respect to Tl^{III} and quinol. Any particular run has been found to give linear plot upto about 75% of the reaction. The work is found to be reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

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TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF RATE ON Tl^{III} AND QUINOL IN 75% ACETIC ACID AT 30°

$[Tl^{III}] \times 10^3 M$	$[Quinol] \times 10^3 M$	$10^3 k_1$ min ⁻¹
5.00	10.00	16.56 ± 0.02
5.00	5.00	12.23 ± 0.01
5.00	3.33	8.08 ± 0.04
5.00	2.50	6.06 ± 0.04
4.00	2.50	6.10 ± 0.08
3.88	2.50	6.10 ± 0.02
2.85	2.50	6.19 ± 0.03

Effect of temperature on rate constant: The values of thermodynamic parameters are recorded in Table 2. The Arrhenius law was found to be valid.

 TABLE 2—EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON RATE CONSTANT
 $10^3([Tl^{III}]=5.0 M; 10^3[Quinol]=2.5 M;$
 $HOAc=75\% (v/v))$

Temp. K	$10^3 k$ min ⁻¹	ΔS e.u.	$PZ \times 10^7$ min ⁻¹	ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔF kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔE kcal mol ⁻¹
303	6.06 ± 0.04	-24.48	1.288	13.55	20.97	
309	9.74 ± 0.02	-24.32	1.119	13.54	21.08	14.414
318	19.76 ± 0.09	-24.30	1.972	13.53	21.14	(mean)
318	19.36 ± 0.02	-24.48	1.299	13.23	21.02	

Effect of solvent composition on rate constant: The solvent composition was studied in the range 75-100% and the results show that the rate increases on increasing the percent composition of acetic acid. This observation is similar to that recorded earlier¹⁸⁻²¹ in the oxidation by chromic acid and Tl^{III} of alcohols, mandelic acid, glycollic acid, benzoic acid, etc. This may be explained on the basis that the increase in the acetic acid concentration decreases the dielectric constant of the solvent²².

It is known¹⁸ that in the higher acid concentration range, the proton abstracts an acetate group from thallic triacetate

The species $Tl(OAc)_2^+$ being more active than $Tl(OAc)_3$ leads to increasing rate of oxidation.

Salt effect on the reaction: Varying concentrations of sodium chloride and sodium sulphate have been found to exert no effect on the reaction rate. However, the rate was retarded by increasing the concentration of sodium acetate (Table 3).

The retarding effect of sodium acetate may be due to the formation of less reactive species like $Tl(OAc)^{4-}$ as suggested earlier^{18,19}.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF SODIUM ACETATE

$[NaOAc] M$	$10^3 k_1$ (min ⁻¹)
0.000	4.270 ± 0.02
1.50	3.101 ± 0.08
200	2.320 ± 0.02
2.50	1.420 ± 0.01

Reaction mechanism: When oxidant and organic substrate were mixed together a golden yellow colour was developed having optical density 0.48 at λ_{max} 440 nm which gradually faded to light yellow colour having optical density 0.24 at the same wavelength. It may be concluded that the reaction proceeded through complex formation which slowly decomposed to form product through free radical mechanism.

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